

Dear reader,

As the year 2022 draws to a close, we'd like to bring the progress of our ySKILLS research to your attention. It was a year in which we once again took to the schools in our six focal countries. Besides a school survey (wave 2), we also conducted four in-depth studies in which we focused on children and young people in an at-risk situation or with vulnerabilities.

You can read all about it in this Newsletter. In addition to reports, we have webinars, infographics, and an interactive report in store for you.

Hopefully the holiday season will bring you some rest and time to browse our ySKILLS achievements.

The entire ySKILLS team wishes you a great end of the year. May 2023 be a better year for the world with positive new beginnings. All of us at ySKILLS will continue our unabated commitment to our research on children and young people in 2023.

Happy New Year to All of You!

The ySKILLS team

WORKING MOMENTS

Oslo, 3-4 May: the workshop with [DigiGen](#), [DigiMatex](#) and [CO:RE](#) allowed us to exchange experiences on researching children's and young people's digital lives.

Leuven, 10-11 November: the ySKILLS general assembly discussed the project recommendations for different stakeholders.

Discussing new data of ySKILLS research

A visual representation of ySKILLS by Laura Sorvala

CONCLUSIONS FROM YSKILLS IN-DEPTH STUDIES

These studies intended to gain an in-depth understanding of the role of digital skills in improving or undermining at-risk (vulnerable or disadvantaged) children's wellbeing, by fostering their coping and online resilience.

NON-FORMAL LEARNING CONTEXTS

Participant countries: Belgium, Denmark, and Italy.

One-fits-all solutions and "open doors" workshops do not necessarily ensure the diversity of participants.

Digital skills activities that are close to children's interests, competencies, experiences and needs improve inclusivity and engagement.

An open door workshop in Italy.

RECOGNIZING MIS- AND DISINFORMATION

Participant countries: Belgium, Czech Republic, and Finland.

Most participants are aware of social media logics to some extent.

Most participants' responses were rather operational and technical than critical, and based on their daily experiences in the digital world and their own observations.

Example of task on the performance test.

YOUNG PEOPLE WITH MENTAL DIFFICULTIES

Participant countries: Norway and United Kingdom.

Our adolescents talked of active strategies of avoidance and developing digital skills designed to keep their experiences secret from parents, teachers, therapists and even peers.

The advice given by adults was widely regarded as unrealistic or out of touch, failing to understand young people's digital commitments, however risky.

Talking about the most used apps in the workshop.

YOUNG REFUGEES

Participant countries: Belgium, Greece, and United Kingdom.

Some young refugees have never used smartphones or computers before migrating, others have grown up with them.

Risky choices include deliberately disconnecting from their phones under precarious situations so that authorities cannot use GPS technologies to track them, or connecting with trafficker networks as this is the only way for some to reach safety.

Filling the asset mapping with risks and necessities of internet use.

CHECK OTHER KEY FINDINGS, CALLS TO ACTION AND FINAL REPORTS IN THE [INTERACTIVE REPORT](#)

Vulnerabilities and digital skills

How do digital skills develop, evolve, and affect children and young people in vulnerable situations? Our four studies explore this question.

2ND WAVE OF LONGITUDINAL SURVEY

We got back to the schools and conducted the same survey about reported digital skills, with the same students. Some of them also conducted performance tests.

Who participated?

7,133 adolescents

3,942 participated in waves 1 and 2

Gender

Age

Participant countries: Estonia, Finland, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Portugal.

2ND WAVE: SMALL IMPROVEMENT IN THE HIGH SELF-REPORTED SKILLS

Communication and interaction skills

Technological and operational skills

Content creation and production skills

Information and navigation skills

Fact sheets with basic data in national language and English available [here](#).

[Report](#) and [blog post](#) from lessons learned on the performance tests.

PERFORMANCE TESTS

An example of a communication task. Participants had to select the messages that were problematic.

Designing and Data collection

Two modules on information and content creation (774 participants) and another on communication and interaction (724 participants). Data collection was conducted in some classes from the longitudinal survey sample.

A key lesson from test development:

Involve children early in the process of designing performance tests and take their level of understanding and experience as a starting point in the design process.

EXAMPLES OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL DISSEMINATION

Conferences and meetings

ySKILLS participated in two panels at [ECREA](#), Aarhus:

- How to generate impact with research on children and teenagers' digital skills? Insights from two H2020 projects, DigiGen and ySKILLS
- Methodological and Societal Issues Emerging in Research on Digital Skills of Young People: Reflections on Data Collection and Measurement during the COVID-19 Pandemic

ySKILLS team ran a panel at [ICA](#):

- The Role of Digital Skills in At-Risk Children's and Adolescents' Wellbeing

Sonia Livingstone shared results of the project on the Safer Internet Forum (SIF) and in the Family Online Safety Institute Annual Conference - [FOSI](#) (2022).

Academic publications

Beilmann, M., Opermann, S., Kalmus, V., Vissenberg, J., & Pedaste, M. (2022). The Role of School-Home Communication in Supporting the Development of Children's and Adolescents' Digital Skills, and the Changes Brought by Covid-19. *Journal of Media Literacy Education*. Pre-print, digitalcommons.uri.edu/jmle-preprints/40/

Livingstone, S., Mascheroni, G., & Stoilova, M. (2021). The outcomes of gaining digital skills for young people's lives and wellbeing: A systematic evidence review. *New Media & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211043189>

Vissenberg, J., d'Haenens, L., & Livingstone, S. (2022). Digital Literacy and Online Resilience as Facilitators of Young People's Well-Being? A Systematic Review. *European Psychologist*, 27(2), 76-85. doi: 10.1027/1016-9040/a000478

MORE RESULTS AND NEWS

Recent posts of ySKILLS blogs

- Key lessons learned using performance tests to measure digital skills;
- About fostering young people's digital skills practices in non-formal learning contexts;
- How good are young people at spotting online mis- and disinformation? Findings from a multi-method study
- Digital activities and digital skills of non-binary youth: Reconfiguring the gender paradigm?

All posts [here](#).

Publications

ySKILLS reports and other materials are available [here](#).

Webinars

Vulnerabilities and Digital Skills [here](#).

Youth mental health and internet use: benefits and risks of digital skills [here](#).

How to engage a non-academic public in research results - available [here](#) soon.

Videos

Watch each country's contribution to the ySKILLS project. Videos in national languages [here](#).

Keep in touch!

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